

Application of solar panels in vibration control of building structures

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Abstract: Electricity is the primary source of power generation in the society, generation of which has caused rapid depletion in the natural resources such as coal. Also emission of huge amount of greenhouse gas, mainly carbon dioxide due to the generation of electricity have led to the evolution of green technologies in the environment. Among some green technologies solar panels have emerged as sustainable power generators for the environment. Solar panels are seemed to be the next generation renewable energy sources in the world which can eliminate the use of coal. Solar panels are however seen as promising green energy sources to charge semi-active dampers of structures subjected to stochastic excitations. Advanced control based feedback devices are important for sustainable renewable energy systems especially in solar panels. Specifically, they can guarantee safe working conditions of the platform subject to various forms of environmental loads like wind and seismic wave. This work proposes sustainable energy chargers such as solar panels to charge the semi-active damper to eliminate the dependency on constant power sources, that will cut down the installation, operational, and maintenance costs for the control systems.

The objective of the present study is to develop semi-active magnetorheological (MR) damper control systems to obtain the controlled response of structures subject to seismic loads and optimize the power requirement of the control systems using solar panels. A novel control algorithm with a new semi-active control algorithm consisting of Linear Quadratic Gaussian algorithm will be developed for performance improvement of solar panel charged control system. The coherence of the developed sustainably charged semi-active MR damper in reducing dynamic excitations of the structures is investigated considering the optimum location of the MR damper. The performance of the sustainable green energy harvesting mechanism along with proposed optimal control performance during excitation is evaluated. It may be noted here that use of conventional electricity is totally avoided from the consideration of Green technology i.e. solar panels.

Keywords: Solar panels, Renewable energy generators, Green technologies, Sustainable energy, Optimal control; LQG control, Magneto-rheological dampers

Introduction

Harvesting of Green energy from surrounding vibratory energies has been a part of advanced green energy research in recent times. Some electronics, wireless sensors, electrostatic vibration energy harvester are some of the recent low power devices undergoing applications in this field. However, in numerous applications, it has been difficult to harvest recycled energy from very low vibratory energies. This led to exploration of new control algorithms to improve the rate of energy harvesting both using mechanical and electrical mechanisms.

Various control systems and dampers have been studied to reduce the result of tectonic threats in structures by researchers. Structural control is the one of the most effective way to achieve this goal. Semi-active control damping is found to be far more efficient than active and passive control system. Effective performance of the damping devices has become very important to ensure structural safety and serviceability criteria.

Magneto-rheological (MR) damper [1], [2] seems to be used actively in vibration shielding of structures. The advantage that makes this kind of damper unique is its very low power consumption. Different control algorithms can be used for optimum performance which make it an efficient semi-active damping device. It has the capacity of inducing large forces. Also it has low sensitivity to temperature changes. A magneto-rheological damper [3] is filled with ferro-magnetic fluid. This fluid produces shear stress with the induction of magnetic current

through it. Iron particles are present in this fluid carries the magnetic current and align in their respective flux lines. The iron particles help in generating shear stress by acting as an

obstruction to the flow of fluid due to piston movement. The viscosity of the fluid increases within the damper as the current intensity increases and therefore the resistance to flow.

Throughout the years, different researchers have tried to perform the vibration control of building structures by installing MR damper combining with various control algorithms [4]–[6] conducted a comparative study of different conventional control theories i.e., clipped optimal control, decentralized output feedback polynomial controller, Lyapunov theory, simple passive control algorithms etc. to evaluate control force and required voltage for the MR dampers. Rahmanian experimented multi-objective binary coded genetic algorithm [7] to compare with passive control. However, performed a coupled building control where two adjacent shear buildings were considered with semi-active dampers installed in between those buildings. Yang developed control algorithms which were inspired by different other existing algorithms.

The motivation of the present study lies in developing a novel control mechanism to improve the efficiency of green energy harvesting such as solar panel. The next section deals with a semi-active control technique for seismic control of a three degree of freedom base excite system. The present study proposes a semi-active control combining LQG control with clipped optimal control. A controller designed to compute the voltage required to the damper to generate controlled force. The voltage required by MR damper to generate the required damper force is calculated by Clipped optimal control method.

A linear MR damper [8] designed based on Bingham parametric model and is installed to a three storey structural frame to reduce the vibration effect on the frame. MR damper location was optimized. The performance of developed algorithm on the MR damper-frame over a TLCD controlled frame was evaluated. Parametric study has been carried out for four different earthquakes in two different Building frame models.

2.1 Semi-Active Control of Frame

One symmetric structural frame was modeled and dynamic state space modeling of the frame was performed. An MR damper of 100N load capacity is introduced. An linear quadratic Gaussian controller is modeled to evaluate the controlled damper force required to the frame. A clipped optimal control algorithm is incorporated in the LQG control algorithm. The algorithm evaluate the voltage of the MR damper to generate the LQG controller obtained damping force for different seismic excitations. Therefore, the optimized MR damper force reduces the vibration of structural frame up to optimal level. The floor-wise location of the MR damper in the structural frame is optimized.

2.2 Theoretical formulation of MR damper

A benchmark problem of three storey frame is considered with an MR damper to develop a suitable method to control the responses. In this model, in the post-yield area (for a stress greater than the shear stress, H , i.e. for $(\tau \geq \tau_y)$), the MR fluid behaves like a visco-plastic material.

a. Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) controller

Vibration control design on a structural system is obtained considering certain design criteria and conventional control theory [9].

2.4 Clipped optimal controller

The control force and required voltage for the MR damper to produce the required LQG controlled damping force is calculated and controlled using a clipped-optimal controller throughout the simulation.

2.5 Three Storey frame

A structural frame is considered to demonstrate the efficiency of the developed algorithm using four different earthquake data. One three storey structural frame has been adopted. The dynamic model of the frame is provided in the Table 1.

Table 1 System Matrices of the frame

Matrices	Values
Mass matrix	$M = \begin{bmatrix} 98.3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 98.3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 98.3 \end{bmatrix} \text{ kg}$
Stiffness matrix	$K = \begin{bmatrix} 12 & -6.84 & 0 \\ -6.84 & 13.7 & -6.84 \\ 0 & -6.84 & 6.84 \end{bmatrix} 10^5 \frac{N}{m}$
Damping matrix	$C = \begin{bmatrix} 175 & -50 & 0 \\ -50 & 100 & -50 \\ 0 & -50 & 50 \end{bmatrix} \frac{Ns}{m}$
MR Damper force location node	$\Gamma = [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T$
External force location	$\Lambda = [1 \ 1 \ 1]^T$

3. Results and Discussion

Four recorded earthquake data (Fig. 1) are considered to excite the structural frame. These data are NS component of El-Centro (South California, USA) earthquake acceleration data (1940), Lomapreira earthquake (North California, USA) acceleration data (October, 1989), EW component of Arizona earthquake acceleration data (June, 2008), and EW component of Fukushima earthquake acceleration data (November, 2011) respectively.

Fig. 1 Different types of earthquake acceleration data

3.1. Determination of optimum MR damper location

The floor-wise optimum location of MR damper on structural frames has been evaluated in this section. The following models are considered (Table 2) on both the frames to optimize the location of the MR damper to be placed on structural frames. Four aforementioned earthquake data are used to excite both the structural frames.

Table 2 Models considered for uncontrolled and controlled structural frames

Models studied	Type of control used
Uncontrolled structural frame	Uncontrolled
MR damper installed at the top floor	LQG algorithm to produce the damper force
MR damper installed on the first floor	LQG algorithm to control the damper force
MR damper installed on ground floor	LQG algorithm to control the damper force

3.1.1 Optimum MR damper location on structural frame

Top floor responses of the frame have been obtained in terms of time-domain responses (acceleration (Fig. 2) and displacement (Fig. 3) response of the structural frame) and frequency domain responses (first Fourier transformation (FFT) (Fig. 4) and power spectral density (PSD) (Fig. 4.8)) of displacement response. In Fig. 2, uncontrolled and MR damper (at ground floor) controlled responses are scaled-down by 1000. In Figs. 4-5, uncontrolled responses are scaled-down by 10 and 100 to get a better pictorial representation of the output responses. Figures are shown for the east-west (EW) component of Fukushima earthquake acceleration input data (November 2011).

Fig. 2 Acceleration response (top floor) for Fukushima (EW) component of the earthquake-structural frame with lumped mass matrix

Fig. 3 Displacement response (top floor) for Fukushima (EW) earthquake-structural frame with lumped mass matrix

Fig. 4 FFT (displacement) response (top floor) for Fukushima (EW) earthquake-structural frame with lumped mass matrix

Fig. 5 PSD-displacement (top floor) for Fukushima (EW) component of the earthquake-structural frame with lumped mass matrix

Table 3 Maximum displacement (mm) amplitude in the top floor

Earthquakes	Uncontrolled structural frame	MR damper on the top floor	MR damper on the first floor	MR damper on ground floor
El Centro NS	21.98	7.5	8.5	9.1
Lomapreira	22	6.8	9.5	13
Arizona EW	21.9	7.2	11.2	14.12
Fukushima	22	7.2	9.7	12

Table 4 RMS of PSD (displacement (mm)) curve in the top floor

Earthquakes	Uncontrolled structural frame	MR damper on the top floor	MR damper on the first floor	MR damper on ground floor
El Centro NS	10.7	1.2	1.6	1.6
Lomapreira	10.5	1.2	2.5	3.0
Arizona EW	10.9	1.2	2.6	3.1
Fukushima	10.8	1.2	2.0	2.2

Fig. 2-5 can provide a qualitative idea about achieving a maximum reduction of the structural responses through placing an MR damper on the top floor. However, summarized results obtained for all four earthquakes are presented in Table 3-4 to provide a quantitative idea about the amount of reduction in structural responses for different positioning of MR dampers throughout the floors. It is observed from Table 3-4, that when LQG controlled MR damper is placed on the top floor the reduction in the maximum displacement amplitude and RMS of PSD values are within the range of 65-70% and 88-89% of uncontrolled values respectively. In the case of the first floor, the amount of reduction can be found within the range of 48-61% and 76-85% respectively. In the case of the ground floor, the reduction falls within the range of 35-59% and 71-85% respectively. Therefore, the optimum response reduction of the structural frame is achieved when the MR damper is situated at the top floor. In Fig. 2-5, TF,

FF, and GF indicate MR damper placed at the top floor (TF), first floor (FF), and ground floor (GF), respectively.

4. Conclusion

The study consists of proposing a method *i.e.*, a solar power induced combined linear quadratic Gaussian control algorithm with clipped optimal control method for response reduction of structural frame. Solar panels are compatible and sustainable energy to charged semi-active dampers. LQG is a control method for semi-active control systems and is compatible with MR dampers. A clipped optimal control mechanism was utilized to control the voltage produced by the damper. The method shows much efficiency in producing preferable output range in case of varied dynamic time histories. An MR damper is designed linearly to achieve the optimal control force to the frame. Optimal location of the damper is found to be at top floor floor of the structural frame. The performance of an efficient controller can control the vibration of structures significantly. Proposed semi-active control method is efficient in reducing the undesirable displacement of the structural frame due to different types of earthquake data.

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